

Cytokine Profiles and Hematological Alterations in Pulmonary Tuberculosis: A Cross-Sectional Study from Afikpo, Southeast Nigeria

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Abstract

Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the major public health challenges in Nigeria, especially in regions with poor healthcare resources. Chronic inflammation and immune function disruption is triggered by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB), the causative agent of TB. This study was designed to assess Cytokine Profiles and changes in Hematological parameters in TB patients attending Mater Misericordiae Hospital, Afikpo, Ebonyi State, Nigeria. A total of 90 subjects that met the inclusion criteria were recruited for this study. This comprised 45 confirmed TB patients, diagnosed using GeneXpert, and 45 healthy control subjects. Standard laboratory techniques were employed to measure immune response markers, and statistical analyses were performed to determine the significance of the findings. Blood and sputum samples were collected from patients diagnosed with pulmonary (MTB). All collected samples were analysed for full blood count, Cytokines (IFN- γ , TNF- α , IL-10, and IL-12) were determined using micro ELISA. Demographic data among TB patients, indicated that males (27; 60.0%) were more prevalent than females (18; 40.0%), The most frequent age group among TB patients was above 50 years (28.9%). Acid-Fast Bacilli (AFB) testing showed that 51% of TB patients had no detectable bacterial organisms, while 24.5%, 13.3%, and 11.1% had 1+, 2+, and 3+ bacterial loads, respectively. GeneXpert analysis further revealed that 55.6% of TB patients had a medium bacterial load, followed by 26.6% with high bacterial load and 17.8% with low bacterial load. A significant increase ($p < 0.05$) was observed in all assayed cytokines in TB patients compared to the controls. In addition, TB patients exhibited significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) TWBC and differential counts, with higher platelets and platelet indices compared to the control group. There were significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) RBC counts and associated indices in TB patients compared to the controls. Findings suggest a significant T lymphocyte (LYM) activity and macrophage function alteration among TB patients compared to healthy controls. These immunological alterations may contribute to disease exacerbation and progression. Indeed, the noted changes in cytokines and Haematological parameters offer significant biotechnology possibilities for the creation of new diagnostics, testing devices, and immune-modulating treatments for TB.

Keywords: Tuberculosis, Interleukin, Macrophages, T lymphocytes, Immune response, Nigeria

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Introduction

TB remains a public health challenge with significant concern despite numerous efforts to control it, particularly in low-resource regions such as Ebonyi State, where low infrastructure and resources impair effective TB management and control (Olowoyo *et al.*, 2024). TB is a pathogenic disease that spark chronic inflammation and highly infectious through airborne droplets released by coughing, sneezing, speaking, or singing from infected person (WHO, 2011). Global Tuberculosis Report (2020) by World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 10 million people developed TB, with 1.4 million experiencing active disease (WHO, 2020). TB remains a leading global cause of mortality,

particularly in resource-limited settings where socioeconomic challenges and restricted access to healthcare contribute to its high prevalence. Nigeria ranks third among the 22 high-burden TB countries, followed by India and China (WHO, 2021). The persistence and prevalence of TB as a public health threat is due to complex biological and sociological factors, triggered by poverty, overcrowding, lack of awareness, and weakened immune systems (Dodd *et al.*, 2017).

Robert Koch was the first scientist to discover TB in 1882 (Gordon & Parish, 2018). The disease primarily infects the lungs but can result to extrapulmonary TB when spread to other organs (Miggiano *et al.*, 2020). When inhaled, *M. tuberculosis* is engulfed by alveolar macrophages.

However, due to its cell wall composition, such as mycolic acids and cord factor glycolipids, the bacteria are able to evade destruction through inhibition of phagolysosome formation, hence its virulence and survival.

An important part of the host immune response to *Mycobacterium Tuberculosis* (MTB) is phagocytosis, an important role for macrophages, dendritic cells, and neutrophils (NEU), where these immune cells recognize and ingest infectious organisms for destruction (Uribe-Querol and Rosales, 2017). The recognition of MTB by these immune cells is mediated through pattern recognition receptors (PRRs), such as toll-like receptors (TLRs), complement receptors, CD14 receptors, scavenger receptors, dendritic cell-specific intercellular adhesion molecule-grabbing non-integrin (DC-SIGN), mannose receptors, and Fcγ receptors. The interaction of MTB ligands with PRRs sparks the secretion of cytokines by macrophages and dendritic cells, resulting in an IFN-γ-dominated immune response, which regulates the growth of MTB, granuloma formation, and adaptive immunity (De Martino *et al.*, 2019). However, MTB has developed mechanisms to bypass immune defences, allowing it to persist within host cells and speed up disease progression. Though it is protective against various infectious agents, it can sometimes act in a way that is conducive for bacterial survival (Hossain and Norazmi, 2013).

Various cytokines have been reported to be crucial for controlling phagocytosis and immune responses in relation to TB infection. Interferon-gamma (IFN-γ): It is secreted by activated T-cells. IFN-γ increases the antimicrobial activity of macrophages, stimulates ROS and NO synthesis for killing infectious agents, and activates host cells for destruction of pathogens (Canton *et al.*, 2021). Tumor Necrosis Factor-alpha (TNF-α): It is secreted by activated macrophages and other immune cells. TNF-α is crucial for immune cell recruitment, phagolysosome fusion, granuloma formation, and apoptosis of infected host cells (Liu *et al.*, 2017). Interleukin-12 (IL-12): It is secreted by activated macrophages and dendritic cells. It activates naïve T-cells to become Th1 cells, leading to increased IFN-γ production for enhanced immune activation (Ma *et al.*, 2015). Interleukin-10 (IL-10): It is an anti-inflammatory cytokine with an inhibitory action on immune

responses to prevent overactivation of host immune responses. However, overproduction of IL-10 inhibits macrophage activation, leading to bacterial survival and disease progression (Ma *et al.*, 2015). TB outcomes are influenced by the balance between anti-inflammatory (IL-10) cytokines and pro-inflammatory (TNF-α, IFN-γ, IL-12). Intense TB cases are linked to elevated TNF-α, while increased IFN-γ and IL-12 are also seen in diagnosed TB patients (Ansari *et al.*, 2011). Depending on host immunity, disease stage and bacterial load, IL-10 levels can vary, (Basingnaa *et al.*, 2018).

TB remains a critical world health challenge, especially in limited-resource areas, but persistent efforts in public health interventions, research and immunotherapy can help reduce its prevalence and improve patient outcomes. This study aims to investigate the activities of T lymphocytes and macrophages in TB patients at Mater Misericordia Hospital, Afikpo, Ebonyi State, using IFN-gamma, IL-10, IL-12, and TNF-alpha as biomarkers.

Materials and Methods

Ethics approval

Approval for this study was obtained from Ethics Committee of Mater Misericordia Hospital, Afikpo, Ebonyi State with reference number, Ref:MMH/EC/Vol.1/007, in accordance with ethical standard for animal and human research. Absolute confidentiality and anonymity guidelines were adhered strictly.

Study Location

This study is carried out in Afikpo, Ebonyi State, which is located in the southeastern geopolitical region in Nigeria. Afikpo is also referred to as "Ehugbo." Apart from Abakaliki, Afikpo is the second-largest urban settlement in Ebonyi State and is situated in the southern part of Ebonyi State in Nigeria. Afikpo is also the headquarters of Afikpo North Local Government Area in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Afikpo shares boundaries with Akpoha Local Government Area to the north, Unwana to the south, Edda in Afikpo South to the southwest, Cross River to the east, and Amasiri to the west. The geographical coordinates of Afikpo are Latitude: 5° 53' 33.29" N and Longitude: 7° 56' 7.22" E, with a tick population

of 233,300 according to the National Population Commission of Nigeria and the National Statistical Bureau (Brinkhoff, 2022). The people living in Afikpo are predominantly from the Igbo ethnic group, with Christianity as their main religion. However, people from other ethnic groups and different religious beliefs, such as Islam and traditional religion, also live in Afikpo. Afikpo does not have a tertiary healthcare facility, but Mater Misericordia Hospital is operational in Afikpo, with 13 Primary Health Care centers in local government areas in Afikpo. Mater Misericordia Hospital was chosen as the study area because it is the major hospital in the zone where TB patients are diagnosed and treated.

Study Design

A cross-sectional, case-control design was used for this study, convenience sampling to recruit participants was adopted. Sputum and blood samples were collected from participants diagnosed with pulmonary Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB). Samples were collected during patients clinic visit at the Mater Misericordia Hospital Chest Unit between 9:00 AM and 1:00 PM. All specimen were taken to the main laboratory for further analysis.

Study Population

A total of 120 participants were initially recruited and screened, but only 90 participants met the inclusion criteria. This comprised 45 established and confirmed TB patients, diagnosed with GeneXpert, and 45 healthy control subjects. The control group were made up of subjects recruited from the community, such as neighbours, church members, and friends who had no occupational exposure to TB and no family history of the disease.

Inclusion Criteria

Subjects for this study included those diagnosed with TB attending Chest unit of Mater Misericordia Hospital, Afikpo, Ebonyi State. Healthy subjects of all ages were recruited as controls. TB patients that were considered eligible had no comorbidities or coinfections such as HIV/AIDS, hepatitis, nephropathy, cancer, liver disease or other concurrent infections, that could disrupt the

interpretation of phagocytosis and cytokine levels. Only subjects who provided informed consent were recruited for the study.

Exclusion Criteria

Exclusion criteria include subjects with coinfections or comorbidities such as HIV/AIDS, hepatitis, renal or liver disease, cancer, or other concurrent infections. Pregnant women were excluded due to potential immune interference and alterations. Participants who declined or withdrew consent at any stage of the study were excluded.

Sample Collection and Technique

The interviewer-administered questionnaire was structured and used to obtain information on the participants' demographics and relevant clinical information. Blood samples were used in this investigation. Equal volumes of blood were collected from both TB patients and controls. Standard procedures were used in extracting blood samples. Blood collection occurred in the chest unit of Mater Misericordia Hospital in Afikpo. A total of 5 mL of blood was collected from each of the participants. 2 mL of blood was used in an ethylene diamine tetra-acetic acid (EDTA) anti-coagulant container for full blood count analysis. 3 mL of blood was collected in a sterile plain glass tube for serum extraction. In order to ensure the samples' integrity, ice boxes were used in delivering the samples to the hospital's main laboratory (Hematology and Immunology laboratories) for analysis. Full blood counts were conducted as soon as the samples arrived. Blood collected in a plain tube was allowed to clot, then serum was collected in a sterile tube for cytokine analysis. The blood samples were then subjected to a temperature of -20°C in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions.

Laboratory Testing

For both test and control samples, the following parameters were analysed: Full Blood Count (FBC), Interleukin-10 (IL-10), Interleukin-12 (IL-12), Tumor Necrosis Factor Alpha (TNF- α), and Interferon Gamma (IFN- γ).

Full Blood Count (FBC) Assay

The full blood count was measured using a five-part hematology autoanalyzer (Mindray Bio-Medical Electronics Co., Ltd, Shenzhen, China). As soon as the machine was turned on, the start-up process was initiated. This was followed by clicking on the 'Next Sample' icon. This opened a window where the subject's sample information was entered. Blood samples containing EDTA were placed on a roller mixer to mix the samples properly. The container was then opened and placed under the sample probe. Once the start button was clicked, 15µL of blood was aspirated by the probe. After completing the analysis, a single buzzer sound was given by the machine, indicating that the sample container could be removed.

Acid Fast Bacilli

The Ziehl-Neelsen staining method was employed in detecting acid-fast bacilli based on the recommended protocols in microbiology and histopathology.

Specimens or tissues were placed on clean and grease-free microscope slides. The smeared specimens were allowed to dry under the influence of air at room temperature and then heat-fixed by sliding the slide 3-4 times over a gentle flame while facing upwards to make sure that the specimen adheres to the slide. The heat-fixed smeared specimens were immersed in a carbol fuchsin solution. Heat was supplied from the bottom of the slide until steam was formed without causing the solution to dry up or boil. The process was repeated after intervals of about five min to ensure that the stain penetrates the thick cell wall of acid-fast bacteria. After the primary staining, the slides were washed with distilled water. The slides were then decolorized with an acid alcohol solution (3% HCl in alcohol) for 1-3 min, or until there was no more red color released from the slide. The slides were then again washed with water. Counterstaining was done using methylene blue (malachite green, when used) for 1-2 min for background staining. The excess stain was washed off with distilled water. The slides were allowed to air dry in an upright position. Examination was done using the oil immersion lens (100×) of the light microscope. The acid-fast bacilli showed up as bright red or pink rod-like bodies on a blue background. For quality control, control slides of known positive and negative

were prepared along with the unknown sample slides.

Cytokine Analysis (IFN-γ, TNF-α, IL-10, and IL-12)

Following the manufacturer's instructions (Sunlong Biotech Co., Ltd. Manufacturer's manual), the levels of Interferon Gamma (IFN-γ), Tumor Necrosis Factor Alpha (TNF-α), Interleukin-10 (IL-10), and Interleukin-12 (IL-12) were analysed. The sample was left undisturbed after collection for 20 min to allow clot formation. The clot was then removed by centrifugation at 2000 rpm for 20 min.

The standard solution was prepared in small tubes as follows: Tube 1: 300 µL of original STD + 150 µL of STD diluent. Tube 2: 300 µL of STD No. 1 + 150 µL of STD diluent. Tube 3: 150 µL of STD No. 2 + 150 µL of STD diluent. Tube 4: 150 µL of STD No. 3 + 150 µL of STD diluent. Tube 5: 150 µL of STD No. 4 + 150 µL of STD diluent. Subsequently, 50 µL of prepared standards was transferred from each tube to five wells of a microplate.

MicroELISA Assay

In the microELISA strip plate test, the first well was used as the blank. In the sample wells, 40 µL and 10 µL of sample dilution buffer and sample respectively were added to make a dilution ratio of 5. Careful loading of samples into the bottom of the well without making contact with the wall was done. The wells were mixed and covered with the closure plate membrane. Incubation of the wells was conducted at 37 °C for 30 min. Washing buffer was diluted with distilled water (1:30 dilution). Removal of the closure plate membrane and washing with wash solution was conducted five times. In the next process, addition of 50 µL HRP-conjugate to the wells except the blank well was conducted. Incubation and washing were conducted as usual. Addition of 50 µL each of Chromogen A and B was done one after another in each well. To terminate the reaction, stop solution of 50 µL was added to all wells, resulting to a colour development from blue to yellow. Microplate reader was used to measure absorbances after the assay completion 15 min post-addition of stop solution.

Statistical Analysis

Microsoft Excel was used to store the collected data which were subsequently analyzed using SPSS version 27.0. Results were presented as frequencies and Mean \pm SD in tables. Student's t-test was used to compare means between two groups, such as mean values of cytokine concentrations (IFN- γ , TNF- α , IL-10, and IL-12) and hematological parameters between pulmonary tuberculosis patients and healthy control subjects. One-way ANOVA was applied for comparisons between more than two groups. For instance, mean differences among TB patient subgroups classified according to bacterial load (low, medium, and high GeneXpert categories), AFB grades (0, 1+, 2+, and 3+), duration of treatment, and MDR versus drug-sensitive groups where applicable. Chi-square analysis was used for frequency distributions of categorical demographic and clinical variables, including gender, age group, AFB result, GeneXpert bacterial load category, treatment status, medication phase, MDR status, and duration of treatment. Pearson's correlation was used to determine relationships between dependent variables (cytokine levels: IFN- γ , TNF- α , IL-10, and IL-12) and independent variables (haematological indices and disease severity indicators such as WBC count, RBC indices, platelet indices, AFB grade, and GeneXpert bacterial load). The research hypothesis was tested at a p-value \leq 0.05, and results were presented in tables.

Results

This study indirectly evaluated the activities of T lymphocytes and macrophages in pulmonary tuberculosis (TB) patients attending Mater Misericordia Hospital, Afikpo, Ebonyi State. This was achieved by assessing cytokine levels such as TNF- α , IFN- γ , IL-10, and IL-12 as well as various parameters of hematology, including Hb, PCV,

RBC count, MCV, MCH, MCHC, PLT count, TWBC count and differentials such as Lymphocyte (LYM) count, Neutrophil (NEU) count, Monocyte (MON) count and Eosinophil (EOS) count. Results are shown below.

Demographic Distribution

The distribution of demographics for TB patients and controls is shown in Table 1 below. Males were common in the TB patient group, accounting for 27 individuals (60.0%), while there were 18 females (40.0%). In the control group, there were 25 males (55.4%) and 20 females (44.6%). TB patients had the highest number of patients over 50 years old (28.9%), while the control group had the highest number of people aged between 20-29 years (35.6%) and 30-39 years (35.6%).

Acid-Fast Bacilli (AFB) testing showed that 51% of TB patients had no detectable bacterial organisms, while 24.5%, 13.3%, and 11.1% had 1+, 2+, and 3+ bacterial loads, respectively. GeneXpert analysis further revealed that 55.6% of TB patients had a medium bacterial load, followed by 26.6% with high bacterial load and 17.8% with low bacterial load. Regarding treatment status, 64.4% of TB patients were on treatment, while 35.6% were treatment-naïve. Most TB patients (58.6%) were in the intensive phase (first 2 months), receiving Rifampicin, Ethambutol, Isoniazid, and Pyrazinamide, while 41.4% were in the continuation phase (months 4–6), receiving Rifampicin and Isoniazid. TB patients newly initiating treatment (35.6%) formed the largest subgroup, whereas those in their 4th and 5th months of treatment (4.4% each) were the least. The majority of TB patients (73.3%) were drug-sensitive (DS), while 26.7% had multi-drug-resistant (MDR) TB.

Table 1: Depicting Demographic Distribution of TB and Control Groups

Variables	TB subjects Freq (%)	Control group Freq (%)	X ²	P-value
Gender			0.182	0.670
Male	27(60.0)	25(55.6)		
Female	18(40.0)	20(44.4)		

Age (years)				
20-29	8(17.7)	16(35.6)	7.133	0.068
30-39	12(26.7)	16(35.6)		
40-49	12(26.7)	7(15.5)		
>59	13(28.9)	6(13.3)		
AFB result				
0	23(51.1)			
1+	11(24.5)			
2+	6(13.3)			
3+	5(11.1)			
GeneXpert result				
Low	8(17.8)			
Medium	25(55.6)			
High	12(26.6)			
Treatment category				
Treatment naive	16(35.6)			
On treatment	29(64.4)			
Medications				
2 months intensive (Rifampcin, Ethambutol, Isoniazid, Perizinamid)	17(58.6)			
4months Continuation (Rifampcin, Isoniazid)	12 (41.4)			
MDR STATUS				
MDR TB	12(26.7)			
MDS TB	33(73.3)			
Months of treatment				
0	16(35.6)			
1	10(22.2)			
2	7(15.5)			
3	8(17.7)			
4	2(4.4)			
5	2(4.4)			

Cytokine Levels

Table 2 compares cytokine levels between the TB and control groups. In all assayed cytokines in TB patients, there is observable significant increase ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2: Cytokine level of the TB subjects and the control group

Variables	TB patients (n=45)	Control subjects n=45	T-value	P-value
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IFN- γ (pg/mL) (32.3-116.1)	131.2 \pm 61.67	64.89 \pm 116	7.08	0.01
TNF- α (pg/mL) (214.3-468.4)	649.5 \pm 73.9	398.7 \pm 62.6	17.37	0.01
IL 10 (pg/mL) (110.0- 180.96)	354.89 \pm 134.5	144.96 \pm 28.7	10.23	0.01
IL 12 (pg/mL) (50.43 - 93.42)	164.73 \pm 103.92	68.98 \pm 14.15	6.12	0.01

*p<0.05 = statistically significant

White Blood Cell Count and Indices

Table 3 presents TWBC and its indices. TB patients exhibited significantly higher (p < 0.05)

TWBC counts, neutrophil counts, and monocyte counts compared to the control group. However, eosinophil and Lymphocyte counts did not show any statistically significant differences (P>0.05) between the groups.

Table 3: WBC count and it's indices of the TB subjects and the control group

Variables	TB patients (n=45)	Control subjects (n=45)	T value	P-value
TWBC ($\times 10^9/l$) (4-11)	11.3 \pm 12.6	6.1 \pm 1.9	2.37	0.009*
NEU ($\times 10^9/l$) (2.0-7.7)	4.5 \pm 1.8	3.5 \pm 1.3	2.93	0.004*
LYM ($\times 10^9/l$) (0.8-4.4)	5.2 \pm 10.6	2.2 \pm 0.8	1.86	0.069
EOS ($\times 10^9/l$) (0.04- 0.44)	0.08 \pm 0.11	0.12 \pm 0.13	1.63	0.105
MON ($\times 10^9/l$) (0.08-0.88)	1.6 \pm 1.5	0.3 \pm 0.2	5.92	0.01*

*p<0.05 = statistically significant, TWBC-Total white Blood Cells

Red Blood Cell Count and Indices

Table 4 compares RBC parameters between the TB and control groups. TB patients had

significantly lower (p < 0.05) RBC counts and associated indices.

Table 4: RBC count and RBC indices of the TB subjects and the control group

Variables	TB patients (n=45)	Control subjects (n=45)	T value	P-value
RBCs ($\times 10^{12}/L$) (3.5-5.5)	3.7 \pm 0.6	4.8 \pm 0.6	8.643	0.01*
HB (g/dL) 13.8-17.2	8.9 \pm 2.0	13.8 \pm 1.5	10.437	0.01*
PCV (%) (38-50)	27.9 \pm 5.4	38.8 \pm 4.4	10.417	0.01*
MCV (fL) (80-100)	75.2 \pm 9.0	84.3 \pm 4.0	6.180	0.01*
MCH (pg)	23.6 \pm 3.8	26.8 \pm 2.4	4.654	0.01*

(27-31) MCHC (g/L) (320-360)	315.0±16.2	330.4±10.9	5.290	0.01*
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*p<0.05 = statistically significant

Platelet Count and Indices

Table 5 compares platelet parameters. TB patients exhibited significantly higher (p < 0.05) platelet counts and platelet indices than the control group:

Table 5: Platelet Count and Platelet Indices of the TB Subjects and Control Group

Variables	Tb patients (n= 45)	Control subjects (n=45)	T Value	P Value
Platelet count ($\times 10^9/L$) (150-450)	283±72.0	245.3±58.1	1.80	0.078
MPV (fL) (8-12)	10.6±1.3	9.5±0.50	5.46	0.0001*
Plateletcrit (%) (0.22-0.24)	0.26±0.07	0.22±0.02	4.24	0.0001*
PDW (fL) (9-17)	20.04±5.95	12.2±1.84	8.39	0.0001*

*P<0.05 = Statistically Significant

Table 6: The Studied parameters based on GeneXpert assessment categorized as low, medium and high are shown in Table 6. The table shows that the TWBC of the TB subjects increased significantly (P<0.05) among the three categories: low ($6.67\pm 0.82 \times 10^9/l$), medium ($8.27\pm 1.84 \times 10^9/L$) and high ($15.86\pm 2.45 \times 10^9/L$) respectively. There was also a significant increase (P<0.05) in the neutrophil count among the three groups; low ($3.55\pm 0.55 \times 10^9/l$), medium ($4.65\pm 0.74 \times 10^9/L$) and high ($7.46\pm 1.15 \times 10^9/L$). This significant increase (P<0.05) was also observed in the Monocyte count; low ($0.76\pm 0.22 \times 10^9/L$), medium ($1.81\pm 60.41 \times 10^9/L$) and high ($2.06\pm 0.58 \times 10^9/L$) respectively, whereas no significant difference was seen in their lymphocyte and eosinophil count.

The table also indicated no significant difference in the RBC, Hb, MCH, MCHC and MCV of the TB subjects based on GeneXpert assessment of low

medium and high. However, the PLT count showed a significant increase among the groups; low ($238.62\pm 25.92 \times 10^9/l$), medium ($282.25\pm 14.51 \times 10^9/L$) and high ($327.16\pm 42.76 \times 10^9/L$), same with PDW; low (16.62 ± 0.51 fL), medium (18.36 ± 0.75 fL) and high (20.83 ± 1.2 fL) while PCT and MPV were comparable between the three groups.

Furthermore, there was a significant increase (P<0.05) in the level of IFN- γ of low (93.27 ± 2.75 pg/mL), medium (126.18 ± 2.97 pg/mL) and high (163.04 ± 11.81 pg/mL) groups, TNF- α ; low (53.23 ± 25.60 pg/mL), medium (64.70 ± 22.78 pg/mL) and high (74.75 ± 9.02 pg/mL), IL 10; low (183.59 ± 54.76 pg/mL), medium (256.26 ± 89.23 pg/mL), high (462.38 ± 69 pg/mL) and lastly IL 12; low (94.08 ± 2.43 pg/mL), medium (106.34 ± 2.84 pg/mL) and high (333.47 ± 27.27 pg/mL).

Table 6: The Studied parameters based of GeneXpert result (Low, Medium and High)

Variables	Low (n=8)	Medium (n=25)	High (n=12)	P value
TWBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	6.67 \pm 0.82	8.27 \pm 1.84	15.86 \pm 2.45	0.0001*
Neut($\times 10^9/L$)	3.55 \pm 0.55	4.65 \pm 0.74	7.46 \pm 1.15	0.0001*
Lymph ($\times 10^9/L$)	1.51 \pm 0.33	1.43 \pm 0.27	1.56 \pm 0.26	0.444
Mono($\times 10^9/L$)	0.76 \pm 0.22	1.81 \pm 0.41	2.06 \pm 0.58	0.0001*
Eosin($\times 10^9/L$)	0.11 \pm 0.12	0.08 \pm 0.10	0.07 \pm 0.11	0.722
RBC($\times 10^{12}/L$)	3.69 \pm 0.35	3.86 \pm 0.63	3.47 \pm 0.55	0.1743
PCV (%)	29.25 \pm 2.12	28.96 \pm 5.89	25.66 \pm 5.9	0.2011
HB(g/dL)	9.3 \pm 0.91	9.25 \pm 2.21	7.97 \pm 1.68	0.1519
MCH (pg)	26.12 \pm 3.90	24.20 \pm 3.12	22.67 \pm 2.31	0.0581
MCHC(g/L)	31.65 \pm 1.48	31.51 \pm 1.54	30.74 \pm 1.39	0.2863
MCV (fL)	74.63 \pm 3.62	75.25 \pm 9.87	72.58 \pm 7.73	0.6771
PLT count ($\times 10^9/L$)	238.62 \pm 25.92	282.25 \pm 14.51	327.16 \pm 42.76	0.0001*
PCT (%)	0.26 \pm 0.07	0.24 \pm 0.05	0.28 \pm 0.7	0.393
MPV (fL)	11.67 \pm 0.23	11.37 \pm 0.67	11.57 \pm 1.33	0.6332
PDW (fL)	16.62 \pm 0.51	18.36 \pm 0.75	20.83 \pm 1.2	0.0001*
IFN- γ (pg/mL)	93.27 \pm 2.75	126.18 \pm 2.97	163.04 \pm 11.81	0.0001*
TNF- α (pg/mL)	53.23 \pm 25.60	64.70 \pm 22.78	74.75 \pm 9.02	0.0001*
IL 10 (pg/mL)	183.59 \pm 54.76	256.26 \pm 89.23	462.38 \pm 69	0.0001*
IL 12 (pg/mL)	94.08 \pm 2.43	106.34 \pm 2.84	333.47 \pm 27.27	0.0001*

*P<0.05 = Statistically Significant

Table 7 indicated that the Studied parameters based on duration of treatment of less than 2 months and from 3 to 5 months continuation on medication. The table showed a significant reduction in the TWBC and Neutrophil counts while the lymphocyte, eosinophil and monocyte counts were comparable among the two groups.

It was observed that after two months of intensive treatment, the RBC count, Hb, PCV, MCH, MCV, MCHC all significantly improved ($p < 0.05$). The platelet count was comparable between the two groups whereas MPV, PCT and PDW significantly increased. Furthermore, IFN- γ , TNF alpha, IL 12 and IL 10 significantly decreased

after two months of intensive treatment. More so, AFB assessment became negative.

Table 7: Hematological and Biochemical parameters based on duration of treatment

Variables	<2months of treatment (n=17)	>2months of treatment (n=12)	T-value	P-value
TWBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	16.00 \pm 2.64	6.76 \pm 1.76	11.5870	0.0001*
NUE ($\times 10^9/L$)	5.13 \pm 1.42	3.11 \pm 1.45	4.1987	0.0001*
LYM ($\times 10^9/L$)	2.27 \pm 0.94	2.79 \pm 1.41	1.4424	0.1564
EOS ($\times 10^9/L$)	0.09 \pm 0.12	0.05 \pm 0.05	1.2372	0.2227
Mon ($\times 10^9/L$)	2.27 \pm 0.34	5.89 \pm 16.41	1.2671	0.2119
RBC ($\times 10^{12}/L$)	3.35 \pm 0.44	4.14 \pm 0.48	4.5630	0.0001*
PCV (%)	26.82 \pm 5.42	31.67 \pm 0.96	2.8947	0.0059*
HB (g/dL)	8.85 \pm 0.36	10.33 \pm 1.03	3.5641	0.0014*
MCH(pg)	23.03 \pm 3.48	26.25 \pm 3.25	2.7920	0.0078*
MCHC (g/L)	24.77 \pm 3.37	32.54 \pm 1.56	7.4130	0.0001*
MCV (fL)	74.15 \pm 8.61	80.67 \pm 2.75	2.1842	0.0345
Platelet count ($\times 10^9/L$)	281.24 \pm 51.26	296.42 \pm 70.45	0.6731	0.5066
MPV(fL)	9.606 \pm 0.27	10.43 \pm 1.16	2.8477	0.0083*
PDW(fL)	17.41 \pm 1.50	16.33 \pm 1.07	2.1279	0.0426*
PCT (%)	0.21 \pm 0.015	0.23 \pm 0.04	3.1100	0.0044*
IL 12 (pg/mL)	291.77 \pm 58.52	105.12 \pm 3.39	10.9763	0.0001*
IL 10 (pg/mL)	333.75 \pm 115.72	163.22 \pm 40.081	4.8800	0.0001*
TNF- α (pg/mL)	654.71 \pm 21.74	536.06 \pm 22.93	13.9634	0.0001*
IFN- γ (pg/mL)	126.84 \pm 2.71	89.94 \pm 5.33	24.5033	0.0001*
AFB result	1.19 \pm 1.06	0.00 \pm 0.0	4.0091	0.0002*

*p<0.05 = statistically significant

Table 8: The studied parameters based on AFB assessment of 0 count, 1+, 2+ and 3+ are shown on Table 8 showed a significant reduction in the RBC Count, HB and PCV with increase in the AFB count particularly between 0 and 2+. There was

also a significant increase, with a peak at 2+, for TWBC (25.97 \pm 31.52 $\times 10^9/L$), Neutrophil count (6.34 \pm 1.8 $\times 10^9/L$) and lymphocyte count (5.85 \pm 2.93 $\times 10^9/L$). The platelet count, MPV, PDW, IFN- γ , TNF- α , IL 12 and IL 10 all

significantly increased across the four groups whereas while PCT, MCV, MCH, MCHC, eosinophil and monocyte count showed some variations

across the groups, they were statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 8: Hematological and Biochemical parameters based on AFB count

Variables	0 count (n=23)	1+ (n=11)	2+ (n=6)	3+ (n=5)	P value
RBC ($\times 10^{12}/L$)	3.83 \pm 0.45	3.36 \pm 0.47	3.23 \pm 0.18	3.48 \pm 0.19	0.002*
PCV (%)	29.47 \pm 4.76	28.91 \pm 5.91	21.5 \pm 3.01	24.0 \pm 3.87	0.0027*
HB (g/dL)	9.36 \pm 1.78	9.19 \pm 2.19	7.3 \pm 1.80	7.3 \pm 1.38	0.028*
MCV (fL)	77.04 \pm 9.33	74.3 \pm 6.67	74.33 \pm 11.02	69.6 \pm 9.24	0.392
MCH (pg)	24.74 \pm 3.93	23.00 \pm 2.94	22.16 \pm 4.36	21.00 \pm 2.56	0.130
MCHC (g/L)	319.42 \pm 16.91	313.7 \pm 14.75	309 \pm 9.44	302 \pm 14.16	0.107
TWBC($\times 10^9/L$)	7.43 \pm 2.21	11.27 \pm 4.29	25.97 \pm 31.52	11.58 \pm 4.29	0.112
Neut ($\times 10^9/L$)	3.39 \pm 0.50	4.72 \pm 1.27	6.34 \pm 1.8	5.25 \pm 2.2	0.0001*
Lymph ($\times 10^9/L$)	2.30 \pm 1.20	4.86 \pm 4.45	5.85 \pm 2.93	5.23 \pm 3.84	0.007*
Eosin ($\times 10^9/L$)	0.06 \pm 0.07	0.161 \pm 0.17	0.06 \pm 0.07	0.05 \pm 0.07	0.0859
Mono ($\times 10^9/L$)	1.48 \pm 1.32	1.22 \pm 0.72	2.89 \pm 2.74	0.960.89 \pm	0.1039
PLT count	296.04 \pm 66.79	238. \pm 53.32	268.5 \pm 53.32	200 \pm 33.40	0.007*
MPV (fL)	10.12 \pm 1.02	10.75 \pm 1.16	11.8 \pm 1.73	12.02 \pm 1.19	0.008*
PCT (%)	0.25 \pm 0.13	0.29 \pm 0.07	0.29 \pm 0.07	0.29 \pm 0.06	0.695
PDW(fL)	16.38 \pm 1.17	23.1 \pm 6.98	24.33 \pm 7.63	25.2 \pm 6.91	0.0002*
IFN- γ (pg/mL)	113.02 \pm 16.87	126.75 \pm 2.45	155.80 \pm 12.47	176.28 \pm 11.6	0.001*
TNF α (pg/mL)	59.9 \pm 6.55	64.08 \pm 1.56	70.93 \pm 6.40	74.69 \pm 0.9	0.01*
IL 10 (pg/mL)	202 23 \pm 50.45	298.73 \pm 46.08	414.68 \pm 88.29	500.22 \pm 5.99	0.001*
IL 12 (pg/mL)	101.81 \pm 6.29	106.98 \pm 1.98	317.0 \pm 8.16	358.54 \pm 24.6	0.001*

* $p < 0.05$ = statistically significant

Table 9 shows the cytokines based on Naïve (no treatment) and Months of treatment. The table showed that in naïve TB subjects, the IFN- γ (126.99 \pm 2.70 pg/ml), TNF- α (72.79 \pm 4.6 pg/mL), IL 10 (447.73 \pm 71.34 pg/mL), IL 12 (99.74 \pm 74 pg/mL) were significantly increased ($P < 0.05$) compared to those on treatment.

The cytokine values of multi drug resistant TB (MDR-TB) and multi drug sensitive TB (MDS-TB)

are shown in Table 10. The table shows that IL 10 (369.14 \pm 108.70 pg/mL), IL 12 (94.38 \pm 2.18 pg/mL), TNF- α (646.01 \pm 20.03 pg/mL), IFN- γ , (90.11 \pm 5.3 pg/mL, 146) significantly increased in MDR-TB subjects compared to the MDS-TB subjects, (163.22 \pm 40.08 pg/mL), (159.87 \pm 96.55 pg/mL), (539.54 \pm 23.86 pg/mL) and (67 \pm 22.61pg/mL) respectively

Table 9: The cytokines level of the TB patients based on Naive and months of treatment.

Variables	Naïve (n=16)	Months of treatment (n=29)	T value	P value
IFN- γ (pg/mL)	126.99 \pm 2.70	91.27 \pm 7.09	19.31	0.01*
TNF α (pg/mL)	727.9 \pm 46.0	616.55 \pm 58.0	16.59	0.01*
IL 10 (pg/mL)	447.73 \pm 71.34	208.96 \pm 58.62	12.10	0.01*
IL 12 (pg/mL)	99.74 \pm 74	200.59 \pm 114.90	3.48	0.011*

* $p < 0.05$ = statistically significant

Table 10: Cytokine disparities among individuals infected with either multidrug resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) or multidrug sensitive tuberculosis (MDS-TB) are summarized in Table 10 below. In MDR-TB, the levels of IL-10, IFN- γ , and TNF- α were considerably higher, whereas

those of IL-12 were lower, indicating an immune-suppressive environment coupled with an amplified inflammatory reaction (Nemeth *et al.*, 2012). Similar findings were reported in Ghana, where IL-10, IFN- γ , and TNF- α were elevated in MDR-TB (Basingnaa *et al.*, 2018).

Table 10: Cytokine Level of TB patients Based on Presence or Absence of Resistant Gene

Variables	MDR-TB (n=12)	MDS-TB (n=33)	T value	P value
IL 10 (pg/mL)	369.14 \pm 108.70.	163.22 \pm 40.08	6.36	0.0001*
IL 12 (pg/mL)	94.38 \pm 2.18	159.87 \pm 96.55	2.33	0.0244*
TNF α (pg/mL)	646.01 \pm 20.03	539.54 \pm 23.86	14.98	0.0001*
IFN- γ (pg/mL)	90.11 \pm 5.3	146.67 \pm 22.61	8.37	0.0001*

* $p < 0.05$ = statistically significant, TNF α - tumour necrosis factor alpha, IFN- γ - interferon, IL - interleukin

Discussion

This study, conducted at Mater Misericordiae Hospital, Afikpo, Ebonyi State, Nigeria, focused on the indirect assessment of T lymphocytes and

macrophage activity in patients with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (TB). A total of 90 participants were recruited in the study; out of these, 45 people had TB, and 45 appeared healthy as control individuals, with their ages ranging from 27 to 70 years old.

The largest number of TB cases in this study occurred in people above the age of 50 years old, representing 28% of the subjects included in this study. This is in agreement with the view that people are at higher risk because of immunosenescence, comorbidities, institutionalization, as well as possible reactivation of dormant lesions because of stress, disease, or poor health in general. This result can be corroborated by the research conducted by Caraux-Paz *et al.* (2021), stating that TB cases occur predominantly in elderly patients because of reactivation of latent TB due to age.

The study also revealed a higher prevalence of TB among males (60%), consistent with findings from Ugwu *et al.*, 2021 in Enugu State, which indicated a higher TB prevalence in men compared to women. This male predominance has been attributed to genetic factors, particularly X-chromosome polymorphism, which may increase susceptibility to TB in men (Gupta *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, previous research has shown that TB is more prevalent in males than females, particularly in low- resource countries (Horton *et al.*, 2016).

A comparison of cytokine levels between TB patients and controls (Table 2) indicated a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in IFN- γ , TNF- α , IL-10, and IL-12 in TB patients. This increase is expected as these cytokines are part of the immune response to MTB. The immune system, particularly the Th1 response, plays a crucial role in mediating protective immunity against TB, as previously reported by Amelio *et al.*, 2017. The IFN- γ and TNF- α stimulate macrophages, allowing them to eliminate the bacteria. The IL-12 facilitates IFN- γ synthesis, while the IL-10 regulates the immune system by reducing IFN- γ and TNF- α synthesis. This conclusion correlates with the findings of the research conducted by Beig *et al.*, 2023, and Andrade Júnior *et al.*, 2008. Both articles mention increased TNF- α concentrations among the participants suffering from TB.

Table 3 shows the WBC count and indices of TB patients and control subjects. Statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) was found regarding the increased total WBC count, neutrophils, and monocytes, suggesting that the presence of infection triggers an immune response. Leukocytosis and neutrophilia are common in TB because the body fights the bacteria (Gebreweld *et al.*, 2024; Shah *et al.*, 2022).

Table 4 shows the RBC indices. Significant decreases were noted in the RBC count, Hb, PCV, MCV, MCH, and MCHC ($p < 0.05$). These results indicate anemia, possibly due to inadequate nutritional intake, which leads to deficiency of iron, vitamin B12, and folate that are necessary for the production of RBCs (Chhabra *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, bone marrow suppression due to TB infection may cause anemia (Adewole *et al.*, 2024). These results corroborate the findings of other studies conducted in Ethiopia and Kenya (Gebreweld *et al.*, 2024; Ongwae *et al.*, 2023) and a meta-analysis by Abaynew *et al.*, 2023. In this study, the pooled prevalence of anemia among African TB patients was 69%.

There is a marked increase in platelets count, MPV, PCT, and PDW in TB patients as observed from Table 5 ($p < 0.05$). This might be attributed to the pro-inflammatory cytokines IFN- γ and TNF- α , which induce the production of acute phase proteins and thrombocytes (Daniela *et al.*, 2021). Same trend was reported by Ongwae *et al.* (2023), who hypothesized that the increase in platelet parameters could be an adaptive response to TB infection.

Table 6 classifies patients into low, medium, and high bacterial loads based on GeneXpert testing. The WBC count, neutrophil, and monocyte levels showed significant increases based on the bacterial load, indicating an increase in the immune system response to bacterial load. However, there were no significant variations in the RBC indices (PCV and HB) depending on bacterial load, which suggests that anemia in TB is related more to chronic infection rather than bacterial load (Aniesedo *et al.*, 2020). There was a significant increased levels of platelets and PDW with respect to the bacterial load, while there were no significant changes in PCT and MPV levels with respect to bacterial load, implying that platelet activation does not depend on bacterial

load (Tozkoparan *et al.*, 2007). Cytokines (IFN- γ , TNF- α , IL-10, and IL-12) also increased with bacterial load, indicating an intensified immune response (Sia & Rengarajan, 2019).

Table 7 shows the effects of intensive TB therapy on study parameters two months into the experiment. A significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) in the count of total WBC and neutrophils implies a reduced level of inflammation. On the other hand, there were improvements in RBC parameters (RBC count, PCV, HB, MCH, MCHC, and MCV) with statistical significance ($p < 0.05$), implying the recovery from anemia as a result of improved nutrition and reduced infections. There was no change in the platelets count, although there were statistically significant increases ($p < 0.05$) in MPV, PDW, and PCT, which may be an indication of platelet activation in wound healing (Ștefanescu *et al.*, 2021). A decrease ($p < 0.05$) was observed in cytokines (IL-12, IL-10, TNF- α , and IFN- γ), indicating that bacteria have been successfully eliminated (Wenjuan *et al.*, 2020; Mary *et al.*, 2020). Notably, AFB results became negative post-treatment, confirming bacterial eradication (Kusmiati *et al.*, 2020).

The patients' categorization according to the AFB levels is presented in Table 8 (0, 1+, 2+, 3+). The RBC count, PCV, Hb, TWBC count, neutrophils, lymphocytes, PLT count, MPV, PDW, IFN- γ , TNF- α , IL-10, and IL-12 had a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among AFB categories, reflecting the importance of these parameters for assessing the severity of the condition. Nevertheless, PCT, MCV, MCH, MCHC, eosinophils, and monocytes were comparable, indicating their limited sensitivity in TB progression monitoring (Xu *et al.*, 2021; Beig *et al.*, 2023).

Comparison of cytokine concentrations in naïve versus treated TB patients is shown in Table 9. In naïve TB patients, there was a significant elevation in TNF- α , IFN- γ , IL-10, and IL-12 concentrations, which indicated inflammation. The cytokines significantly dropped during treatment, showing decreased infection and inflammation (Kaushik *et al.*, 2023).

Cytokine disparities among individuals infected with either multidrug resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) or multidrug sensitive tuberculosis (MDS-TB)

are summarized in Table 10. In MDR-TB, the levels of IL-10, IFN- γ , and TNF- α were considerably higher, whereas those of IL-12 were lower, indicating an immune-suppressive environment coupled with an amplified inflammatory reaction (Nemeth *et al.*, 2012). Similar findings were reported in Ghana, where IL-10, IFN- γ , and TNF- α were elevated in MDR-TB (Basingnaa *et al.*, 2018).

This study found that TB patients had elevated cytokine levels, reflecting an active immune response. Increased TWBC, neutrophil, and monocyte counts suggest heightened immune activation, while reduced RBC indices indicate anemia, a common feature of TB infection. In addition, TB patients had more elevated platelet counts and indices, possibly, suggesting inflammatory responses or a compensatory mechanism in disease pathology. These findings provide strong valuable insights into immune and hematological changes in TB patients, which could aid better diagnosis, treatment, monitoring, and disease management.

Conclusion

The results of this study provide valuable insights that contribute to the existing body of knowledge, offering both theoretical and practical implications. Findings suggest a significant T lymphocyte activity and macrophage function alteration among TB patients compared to healthy controls. These immunological alterations may contribute to disease exacerbation and progression. The study emphasises the relevance of immune monitoring in TB management. **Indeed, the noted changes in cytokines and Haematological parameters offer significant biotechnology possibilities for the creation of new diagnostics, testing devices, and immune-modulating treatments for TB.** Further research is required to thoroughly investigate targeted immunotherapies that could improve patient outcomes in limited- resource settings.

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Declaration of conflict of interest

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

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Cytokine Profiles and Hematological Alterations in Pulmonary Tuberculosis Patients in Afikpo, Southeast Nigeria

Principal Investigator:

Institution:

Questionnaire ID: _____

Date: ____ / ____ / ____

Interviewer Name: _____

Study Group:

- Pulmonary TB Patient
 Healthy Control

INFORMED CONSENT

Have the study objectives been explained to the participant?

- Yes
 No

Does the participant voluntarily agree to participate?

- Yes
 No

Participant Signature/Thumbprint:

Interviewer Signature:

RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE

Study Title

1. Age:

- Under 18 - 18-30 - 31-40 - 41-50 - 51-60 - 61-70 - 70 or older

Marital Status

-Single -Married -widow -Widower -devoiced

2. Gender

- Male - Female

3. Occupation:

- Employed - Unemployed - Student - Retired - Other

4. Education Level:

- No formal education - Primary school - Secondary school - Higher institution - Postgraduate

5. Residence:

- Urban - Rural

Family History

6. Does your house have cross ventilation?

-Yes. -No

7. Has any member of your family been diagnosed of TB before?

-Yes no

If yes,

7a. Have they completed their treatment regime?

-yes. -no

7b. Or is any of them currently on TB medicine?

-Yes. - No. If yes, how many?

8. Has any family member had drug resistant TB?

-Yes. -No. If yes, for how long?

Personal information

9. Have you ever smoked in your life?

-Yes. -No

If yes, do you still smoke?

-Yes. -No

10. Do you take alcoholic drinks?

-yes -No

11. How well do you know about how TB is transmitted?

- Very well. - Somewhat - Not very well. - No knowledge at all

12. When were you told you had tuberculosis (TB)?

- newly diagnosed
- about a month ago
- two months ago
- three months ago
- four months ago
- five months ago

13. what type of TB were you diagnosed with?

- Pulmonary TB
- Extrapulmonary TB
- Both

14. Have you had TB before?

- Yes
- No

15. How long have you taken your medicine

-----have not started, -----within 2 months. ----
-More than 2 months

16. Do you produce sputum easily when you cough?

-Yes. - No

- Worsening

16. Which other symptoms do you experience

-fever

-headache

-weakness

-sweating in the night

-Coughing up blood

17. Do you have any other health conditions?

- Yes. - No - Mention

18. Do you have appetite to eat?

-Yes. -No

19. Have you experienced any issues with taking your medication as prescribed?

- Yes

- No

20. Have you take your medicine daily?

-Yes

-No

21. How often do you attend follow-up visits in the hospital?

-Weekly

- Monthly

- Quarterly

- Less frequently

-not all since I started taking medicine

22. Have you noticed any improvements in your health since you started treatment?

- Significant improvement

- Some improvement

- No change at all